

Micro-Technology for Positioning, Navigation, and Timing Towards PNT Everywhere and Always

Robert Lutwak

DARPA, Microsystems Technology Office

Arlington, VA, USA

Email: robert.lutwak@darpa.mil

Abstract—This paper describes ongoing efforts, sponsored by the U.S. Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency, Microsystems Technology Office (DARPA/MTO) to develop new technology that improves performance and reduces the Size, Weight, and Power (SWaP) of inertial navigation sensors.

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the past decade, the objective of “PNT-everywhere” has become a reality for many applications. Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) receivers with reduced size, weight, and power (SWaP), enable virtually any device to maintain constant knowledge of its position, heading, and time. GNSS PNT availability has enabled a host of disruptive commercial and DoD applications and, consequently, has led to dependency on GNSS for critical infrastructure, navigation, and safety-of-life applications.

Relatively low signal strength and the continuous threat of signal obfuscation due to physical and electromagnetic interference make GNSS PNT inherently fragile. GNSS signals may be degraded under water, underground, and under foliage canopies, as well as in densely populated “urban canyons.” Whether deliberate or accidental, a relatively low-power transmitter at an interfering frequency may cripple GNSS PNT systems. As critical applications become increasingly dependent on PNT-everywhere, augmentation of GNSS is essential.

The objective of the DARPA Microtechnology for Positioning, Navigation, and Timing (micro-PNT) program portfolio is to develop low-SWaP inertial navigation technology as a backup or “flywheel” PNT solution for GNSS augmentation, validation, and holdover in obfuscated environments. Micro-PNT comprises programs addressing the miniaturization of high-performance inertial sensors and timing sources, integration and co-fabrication of multiple disparate sensors, and algorithms for optimum combinatorial PNT solutions in complex application environments.

II. REQUIREMENTS

A. Overview of the Application Space

In general, performance of inertial navigation systems (INS) is specified by Circular Error Probable (CEP) at the

conclusion of a generic mission profile. This has led to broad definitions such as “navigation grade” (1 nmi/hour) or “Tactical Grade” (10 m/min). In practice, however, the requirements and environment of a particular application must be considered to determine the suitability of a particular technology to achieving mission objectives. For example, the requirements for bandwidth and environmental insensitivity vary substantially between airborne and manpack applications, though the required CEP/time may be similar.

Figure 1. Overview of DoD INS navigation requirements

Fig. 1 shows a sampling of DoD applications for INS [1]. All of these applications are satisfied by GNSS PNT, but only the mission space indicated in pink, labeled “SOA MEMS” is, at present, served by INS in a GNSS-obfuscated environment. The other regions of application space define the technology objectives of the micro-PNT program.

At the heart of the INS lies the inertial measurement unit (IMU), which consists of a minimum of seven sensors including a timing reference, three gyroscopes, and three accelerometers. IMU performance is determined by a number of factors, including individual sensor performance as well as their alignment to the platform and to each other in the application environment. Analysis of IMU performance generally requires Monte-Carlo simulation of the mission under a varying trade-space of environmental conditions and device performance. The overall IMU error budget may be arbitrarily divided between the components with consideration provided to SWaP, cost, and other mission requirements. In

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the majority of cases, gyroscope performance and alignment dominate the overall error budget. Because minute errors in orientation result in a misinterpretation of the direction of acceleration, a large error in CEP can quickly accumulate. Consequently, the micro-PNT program has largely focused on improved gyroscope performance in reduced SWaP.

B. State-of-the-Art Gyroscopes

A wide variety of technologies for sensing angular rotation have been demonstrated, including precession of mechanical tops, vibrating structures, and interferometric sensors. In general, gyro performance is limited by the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) and calibration in the short term and by variation of calibration over longer integration times.

Mechanical spinning-top gyroscopes, the workhorse of gyroscopy for most of the past century, have been largely displaced by MEMS and interferometric sensors.

At the very low end of SWaP, tuning-fork gyros (TFGs), based on detection of out-of-plane rotation of an in-plane vibrating mass due to the Coriolis force, are produced in volume by wafer-level micro-electromechanical systems (MEMS) fabrication techniques. SNR, and therefore short-term stability (angle-random walk, ARW) are determined by the suspended proof mass and the total area of the capacitive sensors, which are employed both for driving and sensing the proof mass motion. Consumer-grade TFGs are employed in video gaming and automotive stabilization systems, while higher performance TFGs have been developed for defense applications. In all cases, the TFGs exhibit excellent short-term stability (STS) but suffer poor accuracy as a result of post-calibration variations of mechanical properties, due to relaxation and environmental sensitivity.

Towards the high end of SWaP, optical sensors, including ring-laser and fiber-optic gyroscopes (RLGs and FOGs), sense Sagnac phase shifts between arms of a rotating interferometer. RLGs and FOGs offer superior rotation sensitivity, leading to improvements in both STS and long-term accuracy compared to TFGs. However, optical gyros are considerably more complex and typically require the use of exotic materials and fabrication processes to reduce environmental sensitivity.

Hemispherical and disk resonator gyroscopes (HRGs and DRGs) are an alternative technology based on observation of the motion of an acoustic standing wave excited on an axially-symmetric resonator. These Rate-Integrating Gyroscopes (RIGs) are unique in that the absolute angle of rotation, rather than the angular rate, is observed directly, leading to higher operational bandwidth and elimination of accumulated errors due to integration. The HRG is presently the highest performance gyroscope commercially available [2], though is too expensive for many applications due to requirements for precision assembly and calibration.

Though still confined to laboratory demonstrations, gyroscopes based on atomic physics have shown extraordinary promise for improved accuracy and long-term stability. Technologies under investigation include nuclear magnetic resonance gyros (NMRGs), in which atoms behave as miniature spinning tops, and atom interferometric gyros (AIGs), which are based on the same principles as optical

interferometers but leverage the shorter atomic wavelengths compared to optical sources.

TABLE I. COMPARISON OF GYROSCOPE TECHNOLOGIES

	Comm. MEMS	SOA MEMS	FOG	HRG	Units
Device ¹	ADXRS401	HG1930C A50	DSP-1760	SIRU	
Size	0.15	0.5	500	200	cm ³
Power	0.03	0.2	3	3.5	W
ARW	5	0.09	0.012	2e-5	°/hr ^{1/2}
Stability	50	1	0.05	3e-4	°/hr

Table I summarizes typical values of state-of-the-art (SOA) single-axis gyroscope performance. Atomic technology is not included in the table due to the relative immaturity of engineering, though early laboratory prototypes have demonstrated short-term stability (Angle Random Walk) of $ARW \approx 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ/\text{hr}^{1/2}$ [3].

C. Micro-PNT Program Goals

The objective of the micro-PNT program is to develop enabling technology for low-SWaP inertial sensing. The overarching mandate of the program is “PNT everywhere, on all devices, under all conditions.” While the ultimate cost of the sensors is essential to wide deployment, and preference is given to manufacturable technologies, cost is not an immediate driver of the program.

The micro-PNT program is pursuing the development of advanced sensors for all of clocks, accelerometers, and gyroscopes. As discussed above, however, the majority of the program is invested in gyroscope development, the most challenging and sensitive of the three component technologies.

To address the simultaneous requirements for both high performance and low SWaP, DARPA/MTO-sponsored gyroscope development includes highly integrated and self-calibrating MEMS devices, micro-scale RIGs, improved and reduced SWaP FOGs, and miniaturization of atomic sensors.

III. DARPA/MTO GYROSCOPE DEVELOPMENT

A. Next-generation MEMS Gyroscopes

The primary drivers of long-term TFG inaccuracy and environmental sensitivity, which include misalignment of the capacitive gaps, variations in the strain of the material, and electronic component variability, are observed as variations in the zero-rate output (bias offset) and rotation sensitivity (scale factor), as illustrated in Fig. 2(a), below.

Typically, bias and scale factor are calibrated for each sensor during factory testing but these drift over time, particularly if the gyroscope is held in storage prior to use and/or exposed to extreme temperatures. Ideally, each MEMS gyroscope would be re-calibrated immediately prior to use but this is oftentimes impractical.

¹ Device shown for example only do not reflect endorsement of manufacturer or component

Figure 2. (a) Bias error and scale factor for an ideal and miscalibrated gyroscope (b) TFG bandwidth limitation vs. RIG

The objective of the Primary and Secondary Calibration on the Active Layer (PASCAL) program is in situ calibration of MEMS gyroscopes at point of use, either prior to or during a mission. One approach utilizes “mode-matched” MEMS gyroscopes, with nearly identical drive/sense frequencies, e.g. symmetric TFGs and DRGs. Mode-matched devices enable self-calibration via drive-sense interchange, and thus self-calibration by comparison of response along two orthogonal axes. A second approach is the co-fabrication of a rotational calibration stage with the gyroscope itself, thereby allowing for rotation of the gyroscope for factory-like calibration within the application environment (Fig. 3). The principal challenge with the first approach is the realization of a mode-matched gyroscope and ensuring symmetric drive/sense interchange. Significant challenges with the co-fabrication approach include minimizing out-of-plane rotation and detecting the rate and angle of rotation (calibration of the calibrator).

Figure 3. Co-fabricated rotation stage and TFG (courtesy Sandia)

The ambitious goals of the PASCAL program include stability of bias and scale factor calibration of < 1 ppm over one month, nearly five orders of magnitude superior to SOA.

B. Micro-scale Rate Integrating Gyroscopes (MRIG)

A second limitation of TFGs is illustrated in Fig. 2(b). Because the TFG out-of-plane motion is mitigated by the torsion in silicon support tethers, the scale factor is linear only over a limited operation range. RIGs have no such limitation, enabling use in higher bandwidth applications. In addition, RIGs provide direct readout of angle, rather than rotational rate, thus eliminating the integration of error over time.

The objective of the MRIG program is to develop a high-performance RIG utilizing three-dimensional MEMS fabrication techniques, thereby enabling three orders of magnitude reduction in SWaP, along with significant cost reductions, compared to the macro-scale HRG.

The HRG derives its performance from a highly symmetric wineglass-shaped resonator with extraordinarily high quality factor, Q . Achieving the same performance in a micro-scale device requires the development of novel three-dimensional fabrication techniques and materials systems. MRIG performers are experimenting with alternative architectures, such as the “bundt-cake” resonator shown in Fig. 4, as well as the traditional “wineglass” geometry. Novel fabrication techniques have been developed under the MRG program, including micro-scale glass-blowing, molding, and atomic-layer deposition (ALD). The program is also investigating alternative materials to silicon, including microcrystalline diamond, ultra-low-expansion glass (ULE), fused silica, and metal alloys.

Figure 4. ULE “bundt cake” MRIG fabricated by microscale glass-blowing (courtesy University of California, Irvine)

C. MEMS Integration

The objective of the Single-Chip Timing and Inertial Measurement Unit (TIMU) program is to push the current boundaries of SWaP by co-fabricating an entire MEMS IMU, including three gyroscopes, three accelerometers, and a timing oscillator. TIMU performers are employing a variety of different techniques and material systems to achieve this goal, including a monolithic silicon implementation (Fig. 5) as well as folded and stacked silicon or silica-based TIMUs.

Figure 5. Single-chip silicon TIMU (courtesy Qualtrè and Georgia Tech)

In addition to tight integration and co-fabrication of disparate sensors, the TIMU performance and size objectives require improved MEMS sensor performance, including novel device architectures and fabrication techniques. As a complete IMU, the program goals encompass combined device performance, intra-device cross-coupling and alignment, and environmental insensitivity. The program objective is the demonstration of a complete navigation-grade IMU, with CEP < 1 nmi/hour, within a volume of 10 mm^3 .

D. Interferometric Optical Gyroscopes

RLGs and FOGs observe rotation by injecting light into an optical interferometer in counter-propagating directions and observing the Sagnac phase shift between the emergent

beams. Sensitivity is proportional to A/λ , where A is the total enclosed area and λ is the wavelength of the light. ARW is determined by sensitivity and also by the SNR of the recovered signal. The RLG is an active device, with laser gain embedded within the interferometer, leading to high SNR. ARW of the passively-interrogated FOG is optimized by adding concentric coils of optical fiber, thereby increasing A , limited, ultimately by loss and noise generated in the fiber.

An emerging application of Sagnac interferometry is the integration of an entire optical gyroscope on a single optoelectronic chip, where interferometric cavity would comprise a spiral on-chip waveguide and all components, including light sources, beamsplitters, and detectors, could be co-fabricated on a single low-SWaP, low-cost die. Under the Integrated Photonic Delay (iPhoD) program, performers have demonstrated integrated photonic waveguide technology with an order-of-magnitude lower loss than previously attained, including on-chip waveguide coils of 50 m total length (Fig. 6a), thereby enabling the future development of integrated single-chip Waveguide Optical Gyroscopes (micro-WOGs).

Figure 6. (a) Chip-scale waveguide coil (courtesy U.C. Santa Barbara) (b) Ultra low-loss photonic bandgap fiber (courtesy OFS Specialty Photonics)

Another emerging technology for optical gyroscopy is the resonant fiber optic gyroscope (rFOG). The rFOG is similar to the iFOG except that the fiber coil is a closed loop and is interrogated evanescently. With a high- Q fiber coil, the number of roundtrips through the fiber, and thereby the effective area, A , can be $\gg 1$, leading to enhanced sensitivity and improved ARW. The performance of rFOGs is generally limited by the high loss, polarization mode noise, and Brillouin scattering in conventional optical fiber [4]. The DARPA/MTO Compact Ultra-stable Gyroscope for Absolute Reference (COUGAR) program has developed specialized fiber optimized for rFOG operation (Fig. 6a). iPhoD performers have developed ultra-low-loss photonic bandgap fiber with low-loss transmission, high mode- and polarization-stability, thereby enabling improved rFOG performance.

E. Atomic Gyroscopes

Atomic gyroscopes are an emerging area of interest for micro-scale INS. Analogous to atomic clock technology, sensors based on invariant atomic properties offer potential for intrinsic calibration and high accuracy compared to mechanical devices, whose calibration is determined by machining tolerances.

The NMRG operates on the same principle as the spinning-top processing mechanical gyroscope except that the

spinning mass is the atomic nucleus rather than a mechanical structure. Though the mass, and thereby the sensitivity, are much lower for a single atom, a large number ($> 10^9$) of independent gyroscopes can be contained in a fairly small volume ($< 1 \text{ mm}^3$). DARPA/MTO development of the micro-scale NMRG began with the Navigational-Grade Integrated Micro-Gyroscope (NGIMG) program in 2003 [5] and continues under the Chip-Scale Combinatorial Atomic Navigator (C-SCAN) program. Concurrent advances in micro-scale atomic sensors, under the Chip-Scale Atomic Clock (CSAC) program, further enable micro-NMRG development.

AIGs operate on the same Sagnac principle as FOGs. In general, the enclosed area, A , of the AIG is several orders of magnitude smaller than that of the FOG, but the short (deBroglie) wavelength, λ , of the atoms, compared to the optical wavelengths, compensates for the reduced area. Moreover, because the atoms travel in vacuum, rather than fiber, AIG long-term stability, accuracy, and environmental stability of the AIG is vastly superior to that of the iFOG. AIG sensitivity may be increased by narrowing the atomic velocity distribution and increasing λ via the technique of laser cooling of atoms. Laboratory devices have demonstrated AIGs with $\text{ARW} < 3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ/\text{hr}^{1/2}$ and bias stability $< 6 \times 10^{-5} \text{ }^\circ/\text{hr}$, each two to three orders of magnitude superior to any state-of-the-art technology [6]. Significant technical challenges must be overcome in order to transition AIGs from laboratory-scale instruments to self-contained deployable sensors, including the development of microscale high-vacuum chambers and optical systems, including lasers, optics, phase modulators, and laser frequency control systems.

F. Heterogeneous Sensor Integration

While providing extraordinary bias and scale factor stability, atomic gyroscopes, particularly AIGs, have relatively limited bandwidth, typically $< 1 \text{ Hz}$, due to the required time for atomic state preparation and readout. C-SCAN performers are developing algorithms for hybrid integration of atomic and MEMS sensors for optimal performance on all time scales. The ultimate objective of the C-SCAN program is to demonstrate a complete navigation-grade IMU ($< 10 \text{ m CEP}/18 \text{ minutes}$) with 40 Hz bandwidth, in a volume of 20 cm^3 and power consumption of 1 Watt.

- [1] A. M. Shkel, "Precision navigation and timing enabled by microtechnology: Are we there yet?," in *Proceedings of the ION 2013 Pacific PNT Meeting*, Honolulu, Hawaii, 2013, pp. 1049-1053.
- [2] D. M. Rozelle, "The hemispherical resonator gyro: From wineglass to the planets," in *Proceeding 19th AAS/AIAA Space Flight Mechanics Meeting*, 2009, pp. 1157-1178.
- [3] T. L. Gustavson, "Precision rotation sensing using atom interferometry," Ph.D. thesis, Stanford University, 2000.
- [4] R. Carroll, C. D. Coccoli, D. Cardarelli, and G. T. Coate, "The Passive Resonator Fiber Optic Gyro and Comparison to the Interferometer Fiber Gyro," 1987, pp. 169-177.
- [5] M. Larsen and M. Bulatowicz, "Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Gyroscope: For DARPA's micro-technology for positioning, navigation and timing program," in *Frequency Control Symposium (FCS), 2012 IEEE International*, 2012, pp. 1-5.
- [6] D. S. Durfee, Y. K. Shaham, and M. A. Kasevich, "Long-Term Stability of an Area-Reversible Atom-Interferometer Sagnac Gyroscope," *Physical Review Letters*, vol. 97, p. 240801, 2006.